

UREA ADDUCTS OF FATTY ACIDS. PART VII. COMPONENT FATTY ACIDS OF GROUNDNUT OIL,

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Urea fractionation by decreasing solvent crystallisation method has been applied to the methyl esters of groundnut oil fatty acids. The urea-adducts elution method which gives results on the pattern of elution and displacement chromatography with urea as an adsorbent has been applied to the fatty acid fractionation of groundnut oil. Compositions calculated by urea fractionation fairly agree with the compositions given by other workers.

The fractionation by urea-adduct method has been employed for finding out the component fatty acids of Dalda (Vanaspati) by Mehta, Rao, Rao and Rao¹ and those of mustard oil by Mehta, Rao and Abhyankar². In the present study the fractionation of groundnut oil fatty acids and their methyl esters by urea-adduct method has been undertaken to determine the fatty acid components of the oil. As this oil contains higher saturated acids such as arachidic and behenic, it is of interest to see how these acids can be separated from the mixed fatty acids of groundnut oil.

Methyl esters of the fatty acids have been fractionated by decreasing the solvent and subsequent fractional crystallisation (cf. Mehta *et al.*³, "decreasing solvent crystallisation method"). In order to avoid oxidation of the highly unsaturated acids, the above method has been reversed in the fractionation of fatty acids by urea. It consists of forming the adduct of all the fatty acids in a limited amount of the solvent. The adduct is then successively eluted with a small amount of alcohol every time. From the mother-liquor alcohol is evaporated and the fatty acids or esters are obtained by extraction. The method of eluting the urea adducts of fatty acids by a solvent is analogous to the classical and displacement chromatography with urea as an adsorbent. It is observed that a definite segregation of loosely bound and soluble urea adducts, formed with highly unsaturated and lower saturated components, takes place by this method.

EXPERIMENTAL

Methyl esters of groundnut oil fatty acids were prepared by interesterification of oil (I.V. 90; S.E. 294) by the method followed by Bradley and Johnston³. For the preparation of fatty acids the usual method given by Hilditch⁴ was followed.

UREA ADDUCTS OF FATTY ACIDS

TABLE I
76.74 g. methyl esters of groundnut oil fatty acids (I.V. 90 ; S.E. 294.2) + 220 g. urea + 2.3 litres methanol.

Frac- tion No.	Solvent removed, (W).	Wt. of esters (W).	I.V. (I.V.).	S.E. (S.E.m).	Unstur- esters (W-u).	S.E. of rated saturated esters (W-u).	Approximate Composition								
							Oleic.	Linoleic.	C ₁₇	C ₁₉	C ₁₈	C ₁₆			
1	250 ml.	6.80 g.	1.2	311.7	0.09 g.	6.71 g.	0.09 g.	1.3%	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
1A	...	3.77	0.44	338	0.92	3.75	338.2	0.02	0.53	...	1.64 g.	43.50%	2.11 g.	55.97%	...
1B	...	3.03	2.1	283.1	0.07	2.95	283.2	0.07	2.32	...	...	...	...	1.58 g.	52.25%
2	250	8.20	26.3	284.3	2.52	5.68	279.0	2.52	30.73	...	...	...	...	1.86	22.68
3	400	12.78	79.3	294.2	11.85	0.93	273.2	11.85	92.7	...	...	...	...	0.12	0.94
4	200	10.49	86.8	294.1	10.49	...	...	10.34	98.56	0.15 g.	1.43%	...	...	...	...
5	200	7.22	86.8	283.8	7.22	...	...	7.09	96.2	0.13	1.80	...	...	...	...
6	100	7.28	102	293.2	7.28	...	...	5.90	81.06	1.38	18.94	...	...	...	...
7	100	12.83	112.3	292.7	12.83	...	...	8.88	69.2	3.95	30.8	...	...	...	...
8	Raffinate from No. 7	4.52	140.3	292.0	4.52	...	...	1.67	36.95	2.85	63.05	...	...	...	...
9	Removed completely	5.32	172.0	287	5.32	...	...	0.03	0.55	5.29	99.45	...	...	...	...
Total esters		7944 g.						48.59	13.75	1.44	2.11	3.56	6.20		
% Esters		98.34						63.05	17.92	2.14	2.75	4.45	8.01		
% Acids		98.59						63.05	17.93	2.14	2.77	4.44	8.00		

$$\frac{W}{W+U} \times 100$$

TABLE II
50 g. of groundnut oil fatty acids (I. V. 93.5; N. E. 283) + 200 g. of urea.

No. of ref- erence No.	Amount of EtOH added.	Wt. of fatty acids (W).	I. V. (W).	N. E. (E.W).	Unsat- rated acids (U).	Satur- ated acids (W-U).	N. E. of satur- ated fatty acids.	Approximate Composition								
								Oleic.	Linoleic.	C ₂₂ .	C ₃₀ .	C ₁₈ .	C ₁₀ .	C ₁₄ .		
1	200 ml	4.56 g.	147.5	287.7	4.56 g.	...	...	1.68 g. 36.7%	2.9 g. 63.3%	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
2	200	5.83	144	284.6	5.83	...	...	2.36 41	3.47 59	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
3	200	8.95	128	281.8	8.95	...	...	5.14 57.4	3.81 42.6	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
4	100	4.51	104	285.8	4.51	...	...	3.82 84.5	0.69 15.5	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
5	100	4.22	94.4	283.0	4.22	...	...	4.01 95	0.21 5.0	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
6	100	4.90	86.0	282.8	4.87	0.03 g.	240.0	4.87 99.4	...	...	...	...	...	0.01 g. 0.2%	0.02 g. 0.4%	...
7	100	3.77	75.4	281.4	3.16	0.61	272.5	3.16 84.8	...	...	...	...	0.35 g. 9.3%	0.26 5.9	...	...
8	100	4.35	48.6	273	2.35	2.0	259.6	2.35 54.0	...	...	...	...	0.23 5.3	1.77 40.3	...	...
9	100	1.56	26.2	277.2	0.45	1.11	275.2	0.45 27.8	...	...	...	...	0.74 4.75	0.37 24.7	...	...
10	100	1.27	18.9	301.5	0.27	1.00	307.6	0.27 21.2	...	...	...	0.82 g. 64.5%	0.18 14.3	...	...	...
11	100	0.47	15.8	293.8	0.08	0.39	296.2	0.08 17.0	...	...	...	0.16 34.0	0.23 49.0	...	...	...
12	100	0.36	4.2	309.9	0.02	0.34	311.3	0.02 5.6	...	...	...	0.33 91.5	0.01 2.9	...	...	...
13		2.40	2.6	331.4	0.02	2.38	332.0	0.02 0.8	...	...	1.65 g. 68.6%	0.73 30.6	...	...	...	...
Total acids		47.17	...	...	39.31	7.86	...	28.23	11.08	1.65	2.06	1.74	2.41	0.02	0.02	...
%acids		94.34	...	...	78.62	15.72	...	56.46	22.16	3.30	4.12	3.48	4.82	0.04	0.04	...

Ester fractionation by decreasing solvent crystallisation method.—To 76.74 g. of methyl esters, taken in a 4 litre flask, 220 g. of urea and 23 litres of methanol were added. The mixture was warmed on a water-bath and kept overnight at 29° and the same procedure was followed as reported in Part VI⁶. First fraction was divided into two fractions so as to detect the higher saturated acids separately. To 3.88 g. of the first fraction (L.V. 1.2; S.E. 311.7) 8 g. of urea and 70 ml. of methanol were added. The weight of esters collected were calculated on the basis of 6.8 g. The results of fractionation are shown in Table I.

Fatty acids fractionation by urea-adducts elution method.—To 50 g. of groundnut oil fatty acids 200 g. of urea and 200 ml. of 80% ethyl alcohol (by volume) were added. The mixture was warmed and kept overnight. The adduct formed was filtered through the sintered glass funnel and fatty acids were obtained from the raffinate. To the adduct known amount of 80% alcohol (as shown in Table II) was added and the procedure repeated. The successive elution and collection of fatty acids from the raffinate was conducted as shown in Table II. Finally the residual adduct was decomposed and acid recovered as before.

DISCUSSION

Fractionation of methyl esters (Table I) shows that the separation of higher saturated from unsaturated is well marked. Fraction No. 1, mainly composed of C₁₆ to C₂₂ acids, has an iodine number of 1.2, indicating that approximately 1.3% of oleic acid is present. Fractions No. 4 and 5 with iodine number 86.8 are composed of oleic acid with very little of linoleic acid. There is a continuous enrichment of linoleic acid after the 5th fraction and raffinate (fraction No. 9) is found to be mostly linoleic acid with very little oleic acid (0.6%). The separation of individual saturated acids has also been effected besides the separation of saturated from unsaturated acids. Arachidic and behenic acids have been detected to the extent of 4.91%.

In the fatty acid fractionation by elution (Table II) the relative stability of urea adducts in alcohol seems to be an important factor. Due to the reversible nature of fractionation, as compared with the previous one, it is observed that iodine values progressively decrease. The percentage of oleic acid in the first five fractions increases continuously. The percentage of linoleic acid consequently decreases and separates out completely in fraction No. 5. This is an indication that comparatively linoleic acid is loosely bound than oleic acid. From fraction No. 6 and onwards there is a gradual decrease of oleic acid and increase of saturated acids.

Thus in the mixture of groundnut oil, fatty acids or their esters, urea fractionation proceeds according to the chain length as well as unsaturation. The tendency of urea to bind the acids is found to be more with the less

unsaturated acids than the highly unsaturated and also with higher saturated than the lower ones. The fractionation is fairly selective in the first method due to controlled distillation of the solvent and subsequent removal of the adduct and in the second method due to successive elution with a limited amount of the solvent.

TABLE III

Fatty acid composition of groundnut oil.

Fatty acids.	Decreasing solvent crystallisation method.	Urea-adduct elution method.	Hilditch, Ichaporia & Jasperson ⁶ .	Longenecker ⁷ .	Hilditch & Riley ⁸ .	Hilditch & Vidyarthi ⁹ .
Lingnoceric	...	...	1.1	5.1	6.6	6.5
Behenic	1.58	3.3	3.1			
Arachidic	2.77	4.12	2.4			
Stearic	4.64	3.48	3.1	3.1	4.4	3.0
Palmitic	8.06	4.82	8.3	9.4	8.0	6.0
Myristic	...	0.04	...	0.4	0.5	...
Oleic	63.05	56.46	56.0	54.9	52.5	71.5
Linoleic	17.93	22.16	26.0	26.2	26.3	13.0
Palmitoleic	...	...	Traces	0.9	1.7	...

The component fatty acids of groundnut oil have been calculated on the assumption that fractions are binary mixtures according to the method adopted by Hilditch⁴ in ester fractionation. The compositions obtained by the solvent decreasing method and elution method have been shown in Table III and compared with those published by other workers⁶⁻⁹. The composition obtained by the decreasing solvent crystallisation method shows 5% lower linoleic acid than the elution method. This may be due to the oxidation by repeated heating of the unsaturated acids. This is avoided in the elution method as the highly unsaturated fatty acids are separated first. The composition obtained by this method agrees fairly well with those found by other workers.

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